

EVALUATION OF THE IMPLEMENTED EXTENSIONS TO THE COMPLEX NUMBER IDENTITY PROVER IN GEOGEBRA DISCOVERY

This document provides detailed information about the implemented extensions to the complex number identity (CNI) prover in GeoGebra Discovery¹.

For each extension, it is highlighted whether it was fulfilled (☑), partially fulfilled (⌚), or not fulfilled (✘).

Extension	Assessment	Description
Additional translations	☑	German translations for the CNI proof output are included.
CAS output of declarative point definitions	☑	Declarative point definitions are now displayed explicitly as CAS equations.
CAS output of real relations	⌚	Real relations are now displayed explicitly as CAS equations in hypotheses and thesis. A current limitation occurs when point labels already contain prime symbols, which may lead to incorrect substitutions in later proof steps.
Additional parameter for <code>Eliminate</code>	⌚	An additional parameter controls whether the <code>Eliminate</code> command and its explicit CAS output are shown. Computation may still abort for long-running cases.
Simplification of thesis definition and elimination result	☑	The thesis definition and elimination result are simplified before display.
Removal of subscripts from variable names	☑	Subscripts are removed before passing variables to Giac to avoid misinterpretation of braces.
Additional explanatory proof text	☑	Explanatory proof text is added for newly displayed elements in German and English.
Extended functionality for additional proofs	✘	Further extensions for additional proof cases are not implemented because they were out of scope.

¹ <https://github.com/kovzol/geogebra-discovery>